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Executive Summary

This document is the first Annual Report from the *Digital Twin of the Ocean for Arctic Fisheries* (ARCFISH) project. ARCFISH is a project funded by the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP) program through five national funding agencies in Europe.

ARCFISH will develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) to support the Blue Economy by way of sustainable fisheries in the Arctic, focusing on two key regions: (1) Western Greenland, centred around Disko Bay, and (2) region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and the Barents Sea. In the Arctic, sustainable fisheries are crucial for long-term ecosystem and community resilience. Traditional commercial activities have had negative impacts such as overfishing, pollution, habitat destruction, and climate change have adversely affected ocean health, resulting in declining fish stocks and loss of biodiversity. New data products and services, co-developed with stakeholders, are needed for better decision-making in fisheries management towards a sustainable Blue Economy. For example, in Disko Bay, ecosystem indices could include spatial maps of zooplankton, benthos, shrimp biomass, and upwelling areas. Fisheries and fleet data from Iceland to the Barents Sea could be integrated into the DTO. Potential new services include advanced eLogbooks and spatiotemporal pattern detection and visualization, leveraging digital technologies for cost-efficiency.

Highlights from the first year of the project include:

- Stakeholder engagement strategy developed – How project partners will interact with stakeholders in the targeted regions.
- Dialogue with stakeholders established – Meetings and workshops to identify and understand requirements.
- Initial stakeholder requirements identified – A first set of requirements for the ARCFISH DTO.
- First examples of data products generated – Selected data products with important information for fisheries.
- Digital Twin platform enhancements – New features implemented in Blue Insight platform.
- Outreach launched – Communication tools set up, sample promotional material and events.
- Future work planned – Mapping further development of ARCFISH products, services and platform.

Deliverables produced in year 1 include:

- D1.1 Stakeholder engagement strategy (Gunnlaugsson, 2024)
- D1.2 Requirement specification (Gunnlaugsson and Maar, 2025)
- D2.1 Data ingestion services V1 (Hamre et al., 2025)
- D4.1 Templates for data ingestion and service development (Hestnes, 2024)
- D4.2 Blue Insight DTO V1 - Training Workshop on Data Processing (Nilsen and Hestnes, 2025)
- D5.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DEC) Plan (Higgins and Sá, 2024a)
- D5.2 Project website (Higgins and Sá, 2024b).
- D5.3 Reports on DEC activities V1 1 (Higgins, 2025)
- D6.1 Data Management Plan V1 (Hamre, 2024)

Deliverables and other digital material are available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/arcfish/>.

More information on the project can be found at: <https://www.arcfish.eu/>.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
ARC-MFC	Marine Arctic Monitoring and Forecasting Center
CSV	Comma Separated Values
CTD	Conductivity Temperature Depth
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
FCT	Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia
GEM	Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring
GeoJSON	open standard format for simple geographical features in JSON
GeoTIFF	Geographic Tagged Image File Format
IFD	Innovation Fund Denmark
ISAS	In Situ Analysis System
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LOPS	Laboratoire d'Océanographie Physique et Spatial
MFRI	Marine and Freshwater Research Institute, Iceland
NCBR	The National Centre for Research and Development, Poland
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OPeNDAP	Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol
RANNIS	The Icelandic Centre for Research
RCN	Research Council of Norway
SBE	Sustainable Blue Economy
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
THREDDS	Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Services
TOPAZ	Towards an operational prediction system for the North Atlantic European Coastal Zones
TOR	Task Orchestrator fRamework
VMS	Vessel Management System
WAM	Advanced Wave Model
XBT	Expendable Bathythermographs
XCTD	Expendable Conductivity/Temperature/Depth

1. Stakeholder engagement strategy

The ARCFISH project is developing a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) to support sustainable fisheries in the Arctic, using the Blue Insight platform. The Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE) promotes sustainable development and conservation of ocean resources for economic, social, and environmental benefits. The project focuses on long-term sustainability and resilience of ocean ecosystems and communities in Western Greenland (Disko Bay) and the region around Iceland, northwards to Svalbard and the Barents Sea.

Close collaboration with stakeholders, including fishers, seafood processors, researchers, authorities, and policy-makers, is essential. The project is involving stakeholders throughout the development process, ensuring the final product meets end-user expectations. To avoid stakeholder fatigue, partners are prioritizing stakeholders based on their expertise, interest, and expectations, following a suggested protocol to maintain fruitful dialogue within the targeted regions and the wider Arctic science and fisheries communities (Figure 1).

Project Success and Stakeholder Collaboration

To ensure the project's success, we are working closely with various stakeholders, including fishers, seafood processors, researchers, resource managers, and authorities, to create an Arctic Fisheries Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO).

Workshops and Data Collection to support high relevance of project exploitable results

- **Early Workshops:** Identify data needs and gaps engaging stakeholders in developing digital solutions.
- **Mid-Project Workshops:** Test solutions and gather feedback for improvement.
- **Final Workshops:** Beta test solutions with stakeholders at relevant events.

Capacity Building Workshops will include training tailored to stakeholders' needs.

Stakeholder Engagement The project is maintaining strong stakeholder involvement to ensure everyone's voice is heard and avoid fatigue. The final output will be a white paper on Arctic Fisheries DTO services and applications in support of a Blue Economy.

Figure 1. Process of engaging stakeholders in the ARCFISH project.

2. Meetings with stakeholders

Iceland case study

To ensure meaningful input from a diverse range of stakeholders, the project adopted a strategy of structured individual meetings with each selected stakeholder. This approach not only enhances the quality of contributions during the development phase, but also helps prevent stakeholder fatigue. Stakeholders were identified and prioritized based on their geographic relevance, interests, and expectations. This targeted engagement ensures that project resources are focused on the most relevant and influential stakeholders in the Blue Economy in Iceland, maximizing both efficiency and impact.

During the first year of the project, ARCFISH partners have had several meetings with:

- Brim hf, one of the largest seafood processing companies in Iceland, and a partner in ARCFISH.
- Trackwell hf, an Icelandic software company specialising in developing solutions for the fisheries sector, and a partner in ARCFISH.
- Marine and Freshwater Research Institute (MFRI), a research institute giving advice on sustainable exploitation of renewable resources in the ocean to the Ministry and stakeholders.
- Directorate of Fisheries, responsible for the implementation of legislation in the field of fisheries management in Icelandic waters.

These meetings have identified a first set of requirements for data and functionality in the ARCFISH DTO (see section 3 for a short summary). These requirements have formed the basis for development in the project and will be further refined and elaborated as the implementation of data products and DTO services progresses.

Greenland case study

An online stakeholder event was held on 28. January 2025 for the Greenland case study. Participants from the ARCFISH project were Aarhus University (case study lead and ecosystem modellers), MATIS (stakeholder engagement lead), NERSC (coordinator) and Kongsberg Discovery (DTO developers). External stakeholders included representatives from Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (Pinngortitaleriffik), Ministry of Fisheries and Hunting (Aalisarnermut Piniarnermullu Naalakkersuisoqarfik), Oceans North Kalaallit Nunaat, and Royal Greenland.

After a short welcome and introduction, the ARCFISH team presented an overview of the project and its goals, followed by a demonstration of the Blue Insight platform. Next, plans for a 3D ecosystem model in Disko Bay and how it will help develop ecological indicators for fisheries were presented. During the event, there was ample time for questions and discussions, to identify and clarify stakeholder requirements. This allowed for identifying several key requirements (see section 3 for a short summary), as well as clarifying objectives and planned work in ARCFISH.

3. Stakeholder requirements

The ARCFISH project aims to have results that support scientists, policy makers and resource users to make better informed decisions for sustainable Arctic Fisheries. Therefore, it is essential to develop solutions that are in line with their requests and expectations.

To develop requirement specifications and relevant project outcomes for the two use cases in this project, workshops, brainstorming and individual meetings have been held with stakeholders. The work has included analysing available and missing data, solving issues with sharing the data, identifying what benefits are in coupling the data, addressing privacy issues, and this report suggest functionality for the final solutions and the DTO. Through these activities, the project successfully identified key needs and requirements from stakeholders. However, specific feedback is not disclosed publicly in order to safeguard the developments and innovations that will be pursued during the project lifecycle.

The requirements from different stakeholders are distinct and some are outside the scope of this project. But there are others that can be implemented into the DTO. There are different needs between areas. The Disko Bay is a small area with high interannual variability and there is stakeholder interest if the DTO can support fishery management and predict ecological indices for fisheries in relation to short-term future changes and climate change impacts. They asked if the ecological indices could include maps of hot-spots of productivity and recruitment areas to assist in habitat and larvae protection. For fisheries management, mapping ecological properties and fishing activity (e.g., trawling) could aid legislation and decision-making related to fishing bans or allowances, as well as estimating the impact of trawling and there is interest in the DTO accessibility after the project ends.

The bigger fishing companies will need to adopt standardized methods for sustainability reporting. To efficiently gather and report data, fishing companies will likely need to invest in technology solutions for data collection, tracking emissions and managing environmental impacts. The DTO could be a part of those tools and platforms, supporting environmental and sustainability reporting and supporting them in minimizing fishing effort, while getting the same volumes and values.

The functionality of the DTO for the Directorate of Fisheries could potentially be around the monitoring of possible discard practices. Most of the fisheries are mixed catches with several species, although the captain is usually trying to fish the main species, he has quota for. If the mix of landed fish species not in line with what is expected for certain fishing area, during specific fishing time or season and for the fishing gear used, the DTO could import environmental information for the area to estimate if there are potential changes in environmental factors or zooplankton, that could result in changes in catch composition.

4. Examples of data products

During the first year of the project, an initial set of data products was developed for each of the case study areas. These early outputs aim to support a better understanding of the marine environment and fisheries dynamics in these regions.

A selection of these data products is presented below, accompanied by visualisations created using the Blue Insight digital platform. These data products and visualisations are intended to offer accessible and

informative perspectives for stakeholders engaged in sustainable fisheries and marine resource management, providing reliable tools to support the Blue Economy.

4.1. Fishery-dependent and resource management data

Blue whiting is a small cod fish of great importance for the Icelandic economy. It has historically been used for production of fish meal, for production of aquaculture feed, and fish oil, or in some instances for human consumption. Recent industry trials have shown great potential for further value creation from blue whiting, providing an opportunity for processing the fish for human consumption.

In the first meeting with Brim and TrackWell, it was clear that the fishing company was mostly interested in pelagic species in connection with the digital twin. Especially blue whiting, where the fishing grounds can be difficult to locate, where the species prefers open seas and deep waters. During their lifecycle, blue whiting exhibit seasonal migratory patterns. In the summer months, they are commonly found in deeper waters in the North but during the spawning season, which usually peaks between March and April, they usually migrate to shallower continental shelf areas to reproduce.

Fishing companies are interested in knowing the best location to fish at any given time in line with their legal obligations. Blue whiting is constantly on the move, and it can be a challenge for captains to locate the fish schools. Environmental factors such as salinity, temperature and zooplankton availability can influence the distribution and abundance of blue whiting. A combination of VMS data and fishing data (e.g. catch information) with other relevant data (e.g. ecosystem and resource management data) can have huge potential for stakeholders (e.g. fishing companies, research communities, resource managers, and surveillance sectors). Figure 2 illustrates integration of vessel movement and trawl data into Blue Insight.

Figure 2. Vessel movement and trawl data from Brim pelagic fisheries, displayed in Blue Insight.

4.2. In situ oceanographic data from Copernicus Marine Data Store

The Copernicus Marine In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre (In Situ TAC) provides two essential products:

- NRT_013_002 delivers *Near Real-Time (NRT) data for timely ocean monitoring.*
- MY_013_052 (CORA Analysed Fields) provides *a delayed-mode reanalysis for improved accuracy* (Cabanes et al., 2013; Szekely et al., 2019).

These were developed by the Coriolis team in Brest, France. These global datasets offer high-quality temperature and salinity observations, along with gridded fields derived through objective analysis. Both products are generated using the In Situ Analysis System (ISAS)—a statistical framework developed at LOPS (Laboratoire d’Océanographie Physique et Spatial), ensuring robust quality control, validation, and gridded outputs. ISAS is the operational standard for global in situ ocean analysis in Copernicus Marine. The dataset contains data from different types of instruments: mainly Argo floats (including ITP), CTD, XBT and XCTD, moorings, drifting buoys and sea mammals.

To support fisheries and marine ecosystem monitoring, geographically tailored subsets of these datasets were extracted using Python scripts and Jupyter Notebooks, converted from NetCDF to GeoJSON format, and made accessible via a THREDDS server integrated into the Blue Insight platform. Monthly temperature and salinity fields at 1 m and 300 m depths for January 2024 were visualized in Blue Insight. These are displayed as color-coded points, highlighting spatial variability—a valuable tool for understanding ocean conditions relevant to fish stock distribution and ecosystem dynamics. Currently, datasets for each depth are loaded separately but can be visualized together (Figure 3).

Figure 3. CORA NRT temperature and salinity data at depth of 1m loaded as layers into the scene. Temperature in January 2024 is displayed. The data has a time component and can be shown for other months of 2024. The default map projection is WGS84 (EPSG:4326), with the option to switch to polar stereographic projections (EPSG:3413 or EPSG:3995) for polar region applications.

4.3. In situ oceanographic data downloaded from GEM

Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) is an integrated monitoring and long-term research programme on ecosystems and climate change effects and feedback in the Arctic (<https://g-e-m.dk/>). Since 1995 the programme has established a coherent and integrated understanding of the functioning of ecosystems in a highly variable climate, which is based upon a comprehensive, long-term inter-disciplinary data collection carried out by Danish and Greenlandic monitoring and research institutions.

The GEM Programme puts around 75 scientists in the field annually to collect data on ecosystem and climate change in Greenland. The database currently covers data from monitoring programmes from Zackenberg (1995-), Kobbefjord at Nuuk (2007-) and Disko (2017-). The well over 1000 parameters are freely available via the GEM Database and used by GEM participants and external scientists to produce scientific papers, scientific assessments, advisory reports, etc.

In Disko Bay, the Arctic station is on the Disko Island in central west Greenland. The location is characterized by a low Arctic, coastal climate with some of the world's largest icebergs drifting by. In the MarineBasis folder, under GEM, measurements from cruise and monitoring stations in Disko Bay can be found and downloaded. Data includes CTD measurements of salinity and temperature (Figure 4), Chlorophyll a, nutrients (NO₃, NO₂, NH₄, Si, PO₄), pH, dissolved inorganic carbon, suspended particulate matter concentration and macroalgae growth.

Figure 4. Visualisation of temperature at the depth of 10 m from all GEM cruises in Disko Bay in 2018-2024 in the Blue Insight. Data from all cruises have been collated into one GeoJSON file. Details for each station can be displayed to show measurement date, depth (while the GeoJSON file includes all measured depths, a single depth can be extracted with a user-defined filter), and measured variables (temperature and salinity).

4.4. Ecosystem model products from Disko Bay

Aarhus University has a coupled hydrodynamic-biogeochemical model covering the greater Disko Bay area in west Greenland (Møller et al. 2023, Larsen et al. 2020). The 3D model is implemented in the unstructured marine model framework FlexSem (<https://marweb.bios.au.dk/flexsem>). It has a semi-circular open boundary towards Baffin Bay, where it is forced by interpolated data from the HYCOM and pan-Arctic “A20” models. It includes meteorological, ice-cover and freshwater runoff forcings. The model has a horizontal resolution varying between 2 km in the inner part to 15 km near the open boundary and has been run for the period 2004-2018 (Møller et al., 2023).

As part of the ARCFISH data ingestion service, model data output from the setup has been transferred to Kongsberg to be included in the Blue Insight platform DTO (e.g. Figure 5). AU has provided an integrated C++ and Python API to read the binary native format that stores the unstructured model output and examples of how to read, interpret and present the time varying unstructured 3D data. AU has provided 3D monthly values of temperature, salinity, chlorophyll, primary production, net primary production, light attenuation (Kd), nitrate, phosphate, microzooplankton production, and mesozooplankton production for 2017.

Figure 5. Disco Bay model integrated into the Blue Insight Environment.

4.5. CMEMS met-ice-ocean model forecasts

The Copernicus Marine Service delivers daily 10-day forecasts of key ice-ocean parameters for the Arctic, supporting informed decision-making in fisheries and marine operations. These forecasts are powered by the TOPAZ5 model, developed by NERSC and operated by the Marine Arctic Monitoring and Forecasting Center (ARC-MFC) at the Norwegian Meteorological Institute. TOPAZ5 integrates advanced ocean and sea ice modeling, including:

- Ocean temperature and salinity
- Sea ice thickness and area fraction (Figure 6)
- Physical ocean parameters generated by the CICEv5.1 model

Using a 100-member Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) assimilation scheme, the system ensures high-resolution, data-driven forecasts. Assimilation is performed weekly, producing a 7-day ensemble average, with outputs available at hourly, 6-hourly, daily, and monthly intervals. Forecast data is accessible via OPeNDAP, allowing users to select specific parameters and customize spatial and temporal subsets. These tailored datasets can be seamlessly ingested into the Blue Insight platform, enabling localized analysis and visualization for fisheries management.

Figure 6. Visualisation of sea surface temperature forecast from the TOPAZ5 model in Blue Insight, including pelagic fishing activity data from Brim, marked as short lines in the visualization.

The Copernicus Marine Service delivers high-resolution forecasts of surface wind and wave conditions in the Arctic using the advanced Wave Model (WAM). These forecasts are produced twice daily at a 3 km resolution, offering:

- Hourly forecasts up to 10 days ahead
- A focused 5-day hourly forecast for short-term planning

The WAM model outputs over 20 oceanographic parameters, with key variables including:

- Significant wave height (Figure 7)
- Peak wave period
- Mean wave direction

These forecasts are driven by high-quality input data, including (1) Surface winds and wave spectra from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), and (2) Tidal currents and sea ice data (concentration and thickness) from ARC-MFC.

Forecasts are distributed in NetCDF-4 format and made accessible via OPeNDAP, allowing users to:

- Select specific parameters
- Subset data by region and time
- Integrate outputs into platforms like Blue Insight

This flexibility enables fisheries stakeholders to overlay additional data—such as trawler paths—on top of wave forecasts (Figure 7), enhancing operational safety, route planning, and resource management in Arctic waters.

Figure 7. Visualisation of significant wave height forecast from WAM model in Blue Insight loaded from OPeNDAP servers, including pelagic fishing activity data from Brim .

5. Digital Twin of the Ocean platform

The Blue Insight platform enables flexible data integration from multiple sources—whether from in-situ measurements, partner-generated models, or external scientific datasets. This ensures that fisheries stakeholders have access to the most relevant and up-to-date environmental information.

To promote interoperability with other digital twin systems, Blue Insight prioritizes support for Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) interfaces. It also integrates with widely used scientific standards such as OPeNDAP and THREDDS, allowing direct access to model and observational data in NetCDF format—without the need to duplicate datasets in the platform’s native database.

As part of the ARCFISH project, Blue Insight has expanded its capabilities to include THREDDS catalogue exploration, enabling users to:

- Browse available datasets,
- Filter and load data as points or map layers,
- Or download data for further analysis using tools like the Task Orchestrator fRamework (TOR).

The integration of OPeNDAP into Blue Insight enables efficient, real-time access to remote scientific datasets, eliminating the need for large local storage or full file downloads. This is especially valuable when working with high-volume ocean and climate data relevant to fisheries, making data access simple and flexible:

1. Locate a THREDDS server, or another server offering data access through a standard API.
2. From the data loading interface of Blue Insight (Figure 8), users can choose from multiple sources:
 - OPeNDAP servers
 - OGC-compliant APIs
 - Local OGC-format files (CSV, GeoJSON, Parquet)
 - Cloud-Optimized GeoTIFFs

This integration empowers fisheries stakeholders to quickly discover, filter, and visualize relevant datasets—whether as map layers (Figure 9), data points, or for further analysis using tools like the Task Orchestrator fRamework (TOR). This streamlined approach ensures that fisheries managers and researchers can efficiently access and visualize the data they need—supporting better decision-making and resource management in a changing ocean environment.

Figure 8. The data loading screen integrates several sources in Blue Insight.

Figure 9. Sea ice thickness loaded as layers. If the data has a time component, it can also replay the time.

6. Outreach

During the first year of the ARCFISH project, communication activities focused on establishing a strong digital presence and initiating stakeholder engagement. Partners were also very active in promoting the project at various events and through their home pages in their local languages. While dissemination and exploitation activities are planned for later stages, the groundwork laid in this period is essential for future outreach and impact.

Digital Communication Tools: The ARCFISH project website was launched as the central hub for project information, offering updates on objectives, case studies, results, and events. Designed to be responsive across devices, the site attracted 141 unique users and 226 sessions between October 2024 and March 2025. Most visitors originated from Norway, Portugal, Iceland, and Greenland, with Bergen showing the highest engagement. Analytics revealed that users typically explored multiple pages, with the homepage, “About” section, and “Case Studies” being the most visited.

Complementing the website, ARCFISH established social media accounts on X (@ArcfishEu, #ARCFISH) and LinkedIn (ARCFISH), with a YouTube channel largely reserved for future use. These platforms are used to share project updates, event participation, and partner activities. LinkedIn has emerged as the most effective channel, particularly for engaging professionals in research, business development, and education. Engagement rates on both X and LinkedIn averaged 4%, with notable activity peaks aligning with events involving the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP).

Promotional Materials: A summary poster was created for the 1st Sustainable Blue Economy Symposium and has since been used at various scientific and stakeholder events. The poster focused on the two case

study areas (Figure 10). Additionally, a multi-format brochure was developed and made available online and in print, providing an accessible overview of the project (Figure 11). Both materials are hosted on the [ARCFISH Zenodo community](#) for easy access and sharing.

Figure 10. Illustrations of data, models and software used in the Greenland (a) and Iceland (b) case study areas.

Figure 11. (Left) Front and back cover of the 2025 ARCFISH brochure; (Right) internal pages of the brochure.

Events and Stakeholder Engagement: ARCFISH participated in eight key events, including three conferences, two SBEP meetings, one EU networking event, a webinar organised by third parties, and two stakeholder meetings. These events provided early opportunities to introduce the project to diverse audiences, including scientific communities, industry representatives, and local authorities. Notable events included the European Polar Science Week, the Arctic Circle Conference, and the European Ocean Days.

Endorsement by the UN Ocean Decade: A key achievement for ARCFISH was securing endorsement by the UN Ocean Decade, which bring international visibility to the project, beyond European initiatives.

Overall, the first year of ARCFISH focused on building visibility and laying the foundation for deeper engagement. As the project progresses, these tools and activities will support broader dissemination and uptake among Blue Economy stakeholders in the fisheries and marine sectors.

7. Future work

The ARCFISH project is committed to close collaboration with stakeholders—including fishers, seafood processors, researchers, authorities, and policy-makers—throughout the development of its Arctic Fisheries Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) in support of the Blue Economy. Engagement is structured around a series of workshops to identify data needs, test solutions, and gather feedback. To prevent stakeholder fatigue, the project engages participants based on relevance, interest, and expectations using a clear and manageable engagement process. A mid-term stakeholder meeting will be conducted for each of the two case studies end of 2025 or beginning of 2026. The project is looking for suitable events to meet with the stakeholders physically. During these events, capacity-building sessions will offer tailored training, ensuring stakeholders are equipped to contribute meaningfully to sustainable management and decision making. The process will culminate in a white paper outlining DTO services and applications, reflecting stakeholder input and supporting inclusion for long-term impact.

In its first year, the ARCFISH project focused on integrating key datasets into the Blue Insight digital platform to support data-driven decision-making in Arctic fisheries and marine management. Partners prepared and ingested a range of data types, including in situ oceanographic observations, model forecasts, satellite products, and preliminary fisheries data. Blue Insight’s support for standard formats (e.g., CSV, GeoTIFF) and OPeNDAP protocol enabled efficient handling of large datasets. These were visualized using the platform’s 2D and 3D tools, with global bathymetry and map layers providing geographic context.

Notable data sources included research cruises, operational services, and environmental monitoring programmes. Future additions will include gridded fields from research cruises and Argo float data. More data from the GEM data base, the Disko Bay ecosystem model and new shrimp fishery indicators will be added to the Blue Insight platform. Forecasts from several met-ice-ocean models have been integrated, including CMEMS TOPAZ5 and WAM. These will help create custom products for the ARCFISH case study areas based on stakeholder needs, and more satellite-based products may also be added. Initial fisheries data ingestion included vessel tracks and catch records. These will be expanded to support industry, research, and management needs for the sustainable Blue Economy.

As new products, services, and Digital Twin features are introduced, the ARCFISH project will expand its dissemination efforts through presentations and posters at key community events, SBEP workshops, and scientific conferences, as well as through open-access publications. These results will also be promoted via established communication channels, including the project website and ARCFISH's X and LinkedIn accounts. To further enhance visibility, updated and new promotional materials will be developed, targeting stakeholders across the fisheries sector, environmental management, and the scientific community. These efforts aim to ensure broad awareness and uptake of ARCFISH outcomes as the project progresses. Through these efforts, ARCFISH will help advance the use of Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) technologies and science-based data products in Arctic fisheries, directly supporting the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership's goals of fostering innovation, sustainability, and informed decision-making in marine resource management.

8. References

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